

MODERNITY OF MONITORING AND ANALYSIS

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Abstract: In this article, all participants of the monitoring and analysis process are provided with systematic qualitative information on the quality of educational services, material and technical support of the educational process, the state of legal-normative, strategic, technological, organizational aspects of educational management, the creation of a road map for development, and improvement. It is said that it is a process.

Key words: management, education, production, monitoring, approach, development, quality improvement.

Abstract: This article describes the quality of services for all participants in the educational process, logistics of the educational process, the status of legal, regulatory, strategic, technological, organizational aspects of education management, "Road Map" will be considered in detail. We are talking about development.

Keywords: management, education, production, monitoring, approach, development, quality improvement.

Monitoring. One of the most important tasks facing researchers conducting scientific research today is the development of modern models and technologies for organizing, improving, and determining the indicators of the achievement of educational goals.

There are a number of interpretations of the concept of monitoring, [monitor+visual. ing – action noun suffix] refers to the continuous monitoring of a process in order to determine whether it is in accordance with the expected result or initial assumption. Therefore, monitoring the quality of education means

monitoring and analyzing the level of knowledge acquisition, the formation of skills and the ability to put them into practice during their work or pedagogical activities.

The term monitoring was first used as an alternative to the term "control" on the eve of the Stockholm Conference of the United Nations in June 1972. The elements of monitoring as an integrated system are described and substantiated in the researches of R. Mann, V. D. Federov, K. S. Burdin. Academician R.H. Dzhoraev defines monitoring as collecting, processing, storing and disseminating information in order to provide management of the educational system with information that allows drawing reasonable conclusions about the educational system or its individual elements, evaluating and analyzing its condition at any time. R. Sh. Ahlidinov said that "monitoring is an English term that means "continuous observation". Also, the scientist views monitoring as the most important, relatively independent link in the field of management in the theory of social management, and the results of pedagogical activity are revealed and evaluated within the framework of educational monitoring. Sh. Kurbanov, E. Seytkhalilov in the book "Educational Quality Management" state that monitoring is one of the most important, relatively independent links in the management cycle in the theory of social management. At the same time, it is emphasized that the management, organizational, methodical and pedagogical activities carried out are determined, analyzed and evaluated within the framework of monitoring. It is also explained that monitoring of the quality of education is a complex system aimed at monitoring the state and changes of the quality of education, its assessment and forecasting. In the pedagogical dictionary compiled by G.M. Kodjaspirova, monitoring in education is defined as continuous observation of a certain process of education in order to determine the expected result and the initial suitability. Today, monitoring is an improved tool that provides quality information to the educational management system. If we analyze the types of pedagogical monitoring, we can see the existence of didactic monitoring, educational

monitoring, management monitoring, social-psychological monitoring. In our opinion, monitoring the quality of education is a pedagogical process that allows determining the compatibility of educational goals and achieved results, as well as the factors affecting them, correcting the educational process, and predicting future situations.

Therefore, pedagogical monitoring is a process that provides all participants of the educational process with systematic quality information on the quality of educational services, material and technical support of the educational process, the state of legal-normative, strategic, technological, organizational aspects of educational management, the development of a road map, and improvement. . Monitoring of the quality of education should be carried out according to the classification level and nature of implementation, form, type, function, object, model, periodicity, organizational forms, attitude and purpose. Monitoring the quality of education is a type of activity that allows to collect, process, analyze and make the right decision about the activity of the pedagogical system, its condition and forecasting its development. At the same time, monitoring is an important and independent part of the management cycle in the system of social management theory. The results of pedagogical activities carried out in the monitoring of the quality of education are determined and evaluated, the most important aspect of this process is the establishment of mutual feedback about the suitability of the final results of the pedagogical system. The result of the activity may not always coincide with the goal set for the expected result. This situation allows for a correct and accurate assessment of the reasons for failure to achieve the goal, deviations from the goal, and directions. The reasons for failure to achieve the goal in many cases depend on a number of internal and external factors affecting the pedagogical system.

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